

Problems Faced by School Administrators In The Covid-19 Pandemic Process And Methods Of Solving The Problems

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to examine the problems faced by school administrators in school management and the methods of coping with these problems during the Covid-19 pandemic process. The study group of the research consists of 19 school administrators working in primary, secondary and high schools in the Dilovası district of Kocaeli province in the fall semester of the 2021-2022 academic year. A semi-structured interview form prepared by the researcher was used to get the opinions of school administrators. Interviews with school administrators lasted approximately 20-30 minutes. Content analysis method was used to analyze the data obtained from the interviews. The codes and themes were obtained from the data and the data obtained were shown by preparing a table. From the research, it has been concluded that the problems faced by school administrators originate from teachers, students, parents, physical facilities, technological equipment and senior management. From the research, it was concluded that the methods of solving the problems faced by school administrators are in the form of solidarity and cooperation, benefiting from legal practice, and benefiting from their own knowledge and experience. From the research, the seriousness and strict rules, persuasion, effective communication; hanging posters, eating in the classroom, distribution of masks, disinfectant application; parent education, information meetings, security; Reducing class size, renovation; It has been concluded that the alternative solutions proposed to solve the problems arising from the education system are diluted education, dual system, compensation program, sub-unit in the municipality, in-service training.

Keywords: *School Management, Covid-19, School Manager, Problems*

Introduction

On 31 December 2019, cases of unexplained pneumonia were detected in Wuhan, China. On January 5, 2020, the definition of Covid-19 disease was made and the disease was announced to the world as Covid-19 disease. It was recognized as a pandemic by the World Health Organization on March 12, 2020. The first Covid-19 case was seen in our country on March 10, 2020 (Sertdemir, 2020). The Covid-19 disease, which quickly entered our lives, did not only threaten our health in a negative way. In addition, with the introduction of various bans in the world and in our country, it has caused various problems in economic, social and psychological terms. The education system was also affected by this disease, and schools in our country were closed as of March 16, 2020, and schools switched to distance education as of March 23, 2020. The beginning of distance education instead of face-to-face education, which could not be continued due to the epidemic in our country, and then the transition to face-to-face education brought many problems with it. At all stages of education, including pre-school education, students, teachers, administrators and parents faced various difficulties in keeping up with the situations (Duman, 2021).

The goal of educational administration is to enable people to develop in many ways. School administrators examine how the institution they manage can be developed in accordance with the objectives and effectively. Being a manager in schools requires them to have various educational qualifications as well as the qualities required by leadership. School administrators undertake roles such as providing discipline, mediating relations and conflicts, and making various evaluations. School administrators have various responsibilities and duties such as ensuring continuity in education and training, providing all kinds of educational resources related to the school, and communicating with parents or relevant persons. (Binbaşıoğlu, 1988).

Along with the pandemic, school administrators have taken new responsibilities such as taking the necessary measures to continue face-to-face education. This study will be important in terms of determining the problems that school administrators face during the pandemic process and what solutions are produced to the problems.

The Coronavirus (COVID-19) epidemic, which started in Wuhan, China, continues to threaten the whole world by spreading rapidly in many countries. Countries have taken some measures to protect people from this epidemic, which is described as a pandemic by the World

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Health Organization, and to prevent the spread of the epidemic. The COVID-19 pandemic, which emerged at the end of 2019, has caused significant changes in the economy, social life and education, especially in health.

Education systems are at the forefront of the areas most affected by the COVID-19 epidemic (Can, 2021). Schools in about 190 countries were closed due to the epidemic. This situation affected 92% (1,576,021,818) of the world's students (UNESCO, 2020). The main task of schools in the education system is to organize the environment in order to provide students with desired behaviors and to ensure that certain learning experiences are experienced with students. Keeping the schools closed for a long time due to the epidemic will initially cause disruptions in the education systems, but in the long run it will have negative effects on the economy and the growth of human resources (WORLD BANK, 2020).

The changes experienced during education force the traditional administrator roles of school principals to become a modern education leader (Aras, 2013). solutions are being tried to be implemented (Özer, 2020).

As of the date when COVID-19 cases started to be seen in our country, education in schools was stopped within the scope of epidemic measures and distance education was started. Educational Information Network (EBA), television broadcasting (TRT EBA) and online platforms (Zoom etc.) have been actively used in the education of students in the process after the face-to-face education in schools was suspended.

The cessation of face-to-face education in schools initially caused anxiety in teachers and families, causing some problems (Sarı & Nayır, 2020). The inability of the students to attend school caused them to be deprived of the education service provided at the school, and this situation made the place and importance of the school in the community life to be understood once again (Özer et al., 2020).

The impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on education systems continues, and many countries are trying to adapt their education systems to new emerging situations. The changes caused by the epidemic in the education system have also led to important developments at the school level. Many current issues such as the suspension of education in schools within the scope of epidemic measures, the evolution of face-to-face education into distance education,

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the increase in the importance of school health and hygiene, and the use of technology in education have led to new situations and developments in the management of schools. Changes experienced during education force the traditional administrator roles of school principals to become a modern education leader (Aras, 2013).

In today's world of change, school administrators' educator leadership alone is not enough, and they also need to be sensitive about being open to change and change leadership. should be prepared for possible problems (Çekten, 2006).

Crises are very complex processes and each crisis has its own unique character. Organizations are also at risk of being damaged in crisis situations (Demirtaş, 2000) and every organization may face a crisis situation. The COVID-19 outbreak in 2020 is the most obvious example of this.

School administrations have important duties and responsibilities during the implementation of the decisions taken by policy makers regarding education during the pandemic period. It is necessary to develop and strengthen the reflexes of schools to adapt to the current and developing new situations in an environment of chaos that may arise in times of crisis such as a pandemic (Graduation and Cement, 2021).

This situation has made it a necessity for school principals as leaders to continuously improve their problem-solving processes in management (Çalık & Çalık, 2013). While education and training changed rapidly during the epidemic process and stakeholders were caught unprepared for this sudden change, school principals had to lead by rapidly changing their focus and methods (Kunnath, 2020).

It can be said that the COVID-19 epidemic has led to significant developments and changes in the management of the school. On September 6, 2021, face-to-face training has started at all levels, 5 days a week.

In the "Guide to measures to be taken in schools in the Covid-19 epidemic", prepared in cooperation with the Ministry of National Education and the Ministry of Health and sent to the provincial directorates of national education, it was recommended that teachers, education personnel, canteen workers and student service personnel be fully vaccinated. PCR test is required twice a week from unvaccinated teachers and school staff who are obliged to meet

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with students, all students and teachers in schools are required to wear masks, classroom windows are kept open during the lesson in a way that does not pose a risk to students such as falling and hitting, ensuring natural ventilation, social distance The implementation of articles such as the necessity of complying with the rule of thumb whenever possible has brought along a number of problems.

In the study conducted by Öz Dođru (2021), it was concluded that school administrators faced more than one problem during the Covid-19 outbreak, similar to the problems mentioned above. According to the results obtained from the study, school administrators encountered many problems related to management, communication, economy, planning, school personnel, school climate, school health and education. Considering the findings obtained from the study, the following can be given as examples of the problems encountered: Lack of unity in the implementation of decisions. Various misunderstandings due to the lack of face-to-face communication. Reduction of school income sources. Conflicts in weekly lesson planning. Loss of motivation. Having deterioration in social relationships. Experiencing difficulties in maintaining social distance. The decrease in student participation in lessons are some of the results obtained from the study. Many problems were encountered in the process such as these.

According to the findings obtained from the study conducted by Sarı and Nayır (2020), school administrators encountered various problems during the decision-making processes during the pandemic period, and they encountered difficulties in decision-making, since it was the first time they faced. Based on the findings obtained from the study, the school principals stated that the decisions expressed by the Ministry during the pandemic process were not clear and understandable, that there were frequent changes in the decisions, and that there was no unity in the implementation of the decisions. Such situations reflected negatively on the decision-making processes of school administrators. Another result obtained from the study is that the pandemic process causes stress in teachers. According to the findings of the study, the pandemic process threatens the health of the school, and in this case, it causes both teachers, students and parents to feel bad.

Similar to other studies, in the study conducted by Külekçi Akyavuz and Çakın (2020), school administrators in general stated that they experience various problems arising from

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communication with teachers, students and parents. Another result obtained from the study is that school administrators have problems with planning.

From the study conducted by Gripper and Cut (2021), it was concluded that there was a decrease in the income of schools during the pandemic process. In addition, it was concluded from this study that the problems experienced from time to time with school personnel made school management difficult during the pandemic process.

From the study conducted by Bagwell (2020), it was concluded that school stakeholders experienced great uncertainty during the Covid-19 pandemic process, and the social isolation situation reduced communication and interaction.

According to the findings obtained from the study conducted in Harris (2020), it has been observed that there is an inequality of opportunity among students, and that the internet, computer or education and training tools cannot be reached as desired.

Based on the results of the study above, it can be said that the problems encountered in school management during the epidemic process stem from the fact that such a process has not been experienced before. In line with this information, the problem sentence of the research was determined as follows: What are the problems faced by school administrators during the Covid-19 pandemic in the fall semester of the 2021-2022 academic year, and what are the methods of solving the problems?

PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH

The aim of this research is to examine the problems faced by school administrators in school management and the methods of coping with these problems during the COVID-19 epidemic. In order to achieve this goal, the sub-problems to be answered in the light of the main problem statement are as follows:

1. What are the problems that administrators face in school management during the COVID-19 outbreak?
2. What are the methods of coping with the problems faced by administrators in school management during the COVID-19 epidemic?

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3. What are the suggestions for administrators to cope with the problems they face in school management during the COVID-19 epidemic?

IMPORTANCE OF RESEARCH

Education systems are at the forefront of the areas most affected by the COVID-19 epidemic (Can, 2021). Changes experienced during education force the traditional administrator roles of school principals to become a modern education leader (Aras, 2013).

The impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on education systems continues, and many countries are trying to adapt their education systems to new emerging situations. The changes caused by the epidemic in the education system have also led to important developments at the school level.

Many current issues such as the suspension of education in schools within the scope of epidemic measures, the evolution of face-to-face education into distance education, the increase in the importance of school health and hygiene, and the use of technology in education have led to new situations and developments in the management of schools. In order to achieve success in school management, it is very important to identify the problems encountered in school management and to develop solutions to overcome these problems. In this context, it is thought that determining the problems encountered in school management in the COVID-19 epidemic in line with the opinions of the school principals responsible for the management of the school and offering solutions will contribute to the studies to be carried out on education during the epidemic period.

This research is important in terms of identifying, evaluating and guiding practitioners in the face-to-face education process, which started on September 6, 2021, under the shadow of the Covid-19 epidemic disease, and the effective methods used for them.

METHOD

RESEARCH MODEL

This research; It was designed in a qualitative research model in order to examine the problems faced by school principals in the COVID-19 epidemic and the methods of coping with these problems, and to reveal their views on the process. Qualitative research is defined as

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“research in which qualitative data collection techniques such as observation, interview and document analysis are used, and a qualitative process is followed to reveal perceptions and events in a natural environment in a realistic and holistic manner”. In the scale part of our study, a structured questionnaire was used. The most commonly used method in qualitative research is the interview.

Due to the variable nature of human and society in qualitative research, it has been seen that it is more important to try to understand the facts rather than generalize while examining the subjects. In particular, the effort to deal with social events in a holistic way with their unique dimensions and to reach a deep understanding of the subject matter comes to the fore. Like an explorer, the researcher tries to capture the subjective point of view by following the truth. Another feature of qualitative research is that they are exploratory (Karataş, 2015). The researcher tries to analyze, interpret and make sense of events and phenomena in their own context (Baltacı, 2019).

WORKING GROUP

Since it is not possible to include a sample to represent the universe in qualitative research consisting of non-stationary social events, and it is not intended to generalize in qualitative research, there is no concern for reaching a high sampling rate (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2011 & Kuş, 2007). It is stated that data can be accessed (Baltacı, 2018:244). Patton (2002) stated that with the qualitative method in the research, he could reach a conclusion with very detailed and descriptive information about very few people and events.

The sample of the research consists of administrators working in primary, secondary and high schools in Dilovası district of Kocaeli province in the 2021-2022 academic year. Regarding the problem, 19 people working in primary, secondary and high schools with appropriate qualifications were interviewed. Among the purposive sampling techniques, “criterion sampling” and “easily accessible sampling” techniques were used to reach qualitative data (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2011). In qualitative research, where the size of the data is not important, it is necessary to determine the sample, which will enable the research to reach its

objectives and present the data in a comprehensive and detailed way (Coyne, 1997; Neuman & Robson, 2014).

DATA COLLECTION

During the data collection process, the ways of preparing the research questions, preparing the interview form, determining the study group and conducting the interviews were followed in sequence (King, 2004). A semi-structured interview form was used to collect the research data. One of the most used data collection techniques by qualitative researchers in social sciences is semi-structured in-depth interviews. Interview questions were prepared according to the research sub-problems. The validity of the form was discussed by taking the opinions of 2 experts for the questions. Pilot studies were conducted with 2 participants participating in the program. As a result of the application, the interview questions were revised and the form was finalized.

The data of the study were obtained by interviewing school administrators working in primary, secondary and high schools in Dilovası district. In practice, attention was paid to the volunteering of school administrators. Before the application, the participants were informed about the study. Then, the data collection tool was applied by determining the time periods that each participant was available. During the interviews, the participants were asked what they wanted to ask or add, and then the interview was terminated. The interviews were carried out in a time varying between 20-30 minutes.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

The data obtained from the interviews in the research; It was analyzed according to the content analysis technique and considering the research sub-problems. The purpose of content analysis is to reach concepts and relationships that can explain the collected data. The process in content analysis is to gather similar data around certain concepts and themes and interpret them in a way that the reader can understand (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). The coding process, which is the first stage of content analysis, is defined as the meaningful parts (such as a word, sentence, paragraph) among the data. At this stage, the common aspects of the codes and the classification of those that are in relation with each other are divided into certain categories (Baltacı, 2019). The next step is to gather the classified categories under a theme. The researcher

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organizes the data he has obtained and interprets it according to certain facts. Some principles are taken into account when coding. Whether the emerging theme forms a meaningful whole is evaluated as "internal consistency" and whether all the emerging themes form a meaningful whole with the research data is evaluated as "external consistency". In the findings section, the researcher presents the collected data to the reader. In the last stage, he establishes cause-effect relationships by explaining the relationships between the findings in order to give meaning to the data he collects (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). The data obtained in this research were coded, common expressions were found and themes were found and categorized. The resulting code, themes and categories are arranged and presented in a way that the reader can understand. The findings were interpreted and the conclusion was reached, and these results were conveyed.

FINDINGS AND COMMENTS

FINDINGS RELATED TO THE FIRST SUB-PROBLEM OF THE RESEARCH

Table 1.1. When examined, the themes related to the problems of school administrators; problems originating from the teacher, originating from the student, originating from the parents, originating from the physical facilities of the school, technology originating and senior management.

Table 1.1. Data on Problems Encountered by School Administrators

Category	Code	Quotation
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Teacher-related problems	Not wanting to give PCR testing	Some of our teachers did not want to give PCR tests.P1
	resistance to vaccines	Our teachers show resistance to vaccination.K4
	Teacher shortage	Pregnant teachers did not want to take lessons at the school where there was a shortage of teachers. K7
	We did not have any problems	We did not have any problems.K19

Table 1.1.Data on Problems Encountered by Continuing School Administrators

Category	Code	Quotation
Student-related problems	Non-compliance with social distancing	Our students do not follow the social distance rules.K6
	Absence Not wanting to wear a mask	Absenteeism problems caused by the illness arose.K11
	Being a carrier of the disease	We had problems with mask, distance and hygiene.K18
	Academic decline	The parents sent the sick student to school.K11
	compatibility problem	Students brought the disease in the family to the school environment.P1
	Commitment to school	Children have regressed academically.P1
	Hygiene, cleanliness	We had disciplinary problems in applying the school rules.K4
		Our students had a problem of commitment to the school.K15
	We had difficulties in children's implementation of hygiene rules.K2	

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Problems with parents	Match masks	The parents wanted to enter the school without a mask.K3
	Non-compliance with social distancing	Our parents had problems following the social distance rule.
	Not wanting to enter the schoolyard and building	Our parents wanted to enter the school garden and the building.K19
	Not carrying HES code	We had problems with parents who did not carry the HES code with them.
	Failure to comply with the school entry time	We had problems with our parents about the entrance time to school.K2
	Sending sick children to school	Parents sent sick children to school.P3
	We had no problems	We did not have any problems with the parents.K12

Table 1.1. Data on Problems Encountered by Continuing School Administrators

Category	Code	Quotation
Problems arising from physical facilities	Excess class sizes	The class size is large, this made it difficult to adapt to social distance.K3
	Insufficient width of garden, corridor and stairs	The existing garden, corridor and stair widths of our school were not sufficient.K16
	Sink problem due to renovation	The problem of the number of toilets caused by the renovation in the school forced us.K9
	Guest school, dual system, insufficient building	Another school moved to our school, the number of students increased, we switched to dual education.
	We had no problems	The physical condition of our school caused a serious problem. did not happen.K6

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Problems
caused by
technology
hardware

Internet
infrastructure and
access problem

Since the internet
infrastructure in the
school's environment is
not sufficient, our
students have access to
the internet.

, access to technology is
also limited.K1

Lack of tablets and
computers in
classrooms that
switched to distance
education.

The fact that students
have to connect to the
class by phone
negatively affects the
process.K2

Power outage

Due to the lack of
internet, tablets and
computers, the number of
class participation is low
in classes that transition
to distance education. F
17

We had no

problems

We experienced power cuts
very often.K15

We did not have a
problem because of the
face-to-face training.K4

It's a problem because the
internet is

we did not live.K6.

Table 1.1.Data on Problems Encountered by Continuing School Administrators

Category	Code	Quotation
Top management problems	Insufficient supply of masks and materials	We had a problem with the supply of materials and masks.K11
	Last minute articles, sudden information request, uncomfortable oratory	We had problems with urgent last minute writings and oratory. K 15
	Teacher shortage in classrooms transitioning to distance education	We had a problem with the teacher who would give lessons to some students who returned to face-to-face education.K2
	We had no problems	If you do your duty, there will be no problem.K12

Problems Caused by Teachers

The majority of school administrators stated that teachers did not want to give PCR tests and showed resistance to the vaccine. *“There are some of our teachers who are not vaccinated and they show resistance to vaccination. They did not want to give a PCR test, they think that there is no ban basis.” (P4).*

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With the opening of schools on September 6, there were those who did not want to give PCR tests and did not want to be vaccinated. It was important for us to convince our teachers about this issue so that we could convince parents and students.” (P1). In order to take the pandemic process more seriously on the part of the parents and to overcome the prejudices of those who are against the vaccine, it was emphasized that the teachers should be persuaded about the vaccine and set an example.

The fact that the pandemic process is frightening and schools pose a risk has caused reluctance towards school, especially in pregnant teachers, when it is considered in terms of health. Especially in schools where there is a shortage of teachers, this situation has caused problems. *“The teachers who were 4-5 weeks pregnant at the school, where there was a shortage of teachers during the pandemic period, did not want to take lessons and did not want to spend much time at school, which caused problems.” (P7).* 7 of the participants stated that all their teachers in the school were vaccinated and they did not have any problems with the teachers.

Problems Caused by Students

Table 1.1. When examined, one of the most common problems encountered by all of the participants is the problems arising from the students. One of the most emphasized issues during the pandemic period is social distance. While it is a rule that must be strictly followed in order not to spread the disease, all participants stated that the social distance rule was not followed. *“Because our students are young, they forget to follow the social distance rule, they cannot act as they should.” (K6.)*

During the pandemic process, there are many teachers, students and parents who caught the disease in schools. In case of illness in their families, students cannot come to school because they are in quarantine and are quarantined at home. Likewise, if students get sick, they stay in quarantine at home and do not come to school. This situation caused the students to be absent very often. *“Our students have a problem of absenteeism due to quarantine caused by illness.” (P11).*

In addition, the fact that students were away from school for a long time due to distance education or intermittent quarantines caused problems in adapting to

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school. "With the opening of the schools, we experienced problems with our students in the process of attending school. Because of distance education, they got used to being educated at home, spending time in the home environment and moving comfortably, there were problems in adapting to school, they did not want to come to school." (P1). "As a result of the students being away from school for a long time due to quarantines, we had disciplinary problems in applying the school rules." (P4).

Participants stated that continuing education at home is less productive than face-to-face education at school. They stated that the students experienced academic regression because they could not follow the lessons fully due to the lack of internet, phone, computer and tablet, and this situation negatively affected the motivation of the teachers. *They had regressed in a sense, and this caused a lack of motivation in our teachers.* (P1).

Participants stated that it is mandatory for all students to wear masks at school to prevent the spread of Covid-19 disease, but the children complained about this situation and did not wear the mask as they should. *Our students are not supposed to remove the mask from their faces all day, but they get bored with the mask and open it without realizing it. Our students are young, they cannot fully grasp the severity of the disease process. We had problems with mask, distance and hygiene.* (P18).

The participants stated that the most important thing in this process was cleaning and stated that they had a lot of problems with hygiene. *As the school administration, we put disinfectant in every classroom and corridor. Liquid soaps are always available in our sinks. Although we give extra importance to cleanliness as a school, we had difficulties in enforcing the rules due to the fact that the children do not have much understanding of cleanliness originating from the family and they are small.* (P2).

Problems Caused by Parents

Table 1.1. When examined, in the category of problems arising from the parents; It was stated that the parents wanted to enter the school's garden and

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building without wearing masks and showing the HEPP code."Our parents wanted to enter the school without masks and without showing the HEPP code." (P3). "We had problems with the parents who did not carry the HEPP code with them. Usually, the students did not have the HEPP code with them because their mothers brought them to school." (P1).

Participants; They stated that the parents acted as if the disease was over, they insisted on entering the school building and did not care about the social distance rule, and this caused the spread of the disease."Our parents had difficulty in understanding the seriousness of the incident. They exhibited the behavior of entering the school. They also had problems in complying with the social distance and mask rule themselves." (K10). "Our parents wanted to enter the school garden and the building. Especially our first grade parents wanted to enter the building." (K19).

Participants; stated that students are sent to school very early hours by their families. Students who are sent to school early and without a mask before the teachers pose a problem for the school administration."With our parents

We had problems with the entrance time to the school. They sent the children to school earlier than they should have." (P2).

Three of the participants stated that they did not have any problems with their parents."We did not have any problems with the parents" (P12).

Problems Due to the Physical Facilities of the School

Table 1.1. When examined, the participants in general about the problems arising from physical conditions; They talked about the inadequacy of the width of the garden, corridor and stairs and stated that this situation negatively affects the rule of compliance with social distance."The lack of physical facilities forced us. The existing garden, corridor and stair widths of our school were not sufficient. This

situation made it difficult for students to comply with the social distance rule." (K16).

When the answers of the participants are examined, it is mentioned that another category, the excess of classroom sizes, the increasing numbers due to the guest school arrival, and the insufficient building. Participants mention that the increase in class sizes is negative for the pandemic, making it difficult to adapt to social distance. *"one. and our 2nd graders have a large class size. This made it difficult to adapt to social distance." (P3). "Another school moved to our school, the number of students increased, we had to switch to dual education. Because of this, our students had to come to school early in the morning. All these experiences caused problems during the pandemic period and negatively affected the process." (K14).*

One of the participants stated that they had a lot of trouble due to the ongoing renovation work in their school. He mentioned that the most emphasized issue during the pandemic period was hygiene, while this situation negatively affected the process and put the whole school in trouble. *"The problem of the number of toilets caused by the renovation in the school forced us in this period. Because hygiene is the most important thing for this period." (P9).*

Six of the participants stated that the physical condition of their school did not cause any problems. *"Due to the small number of students and the size of the school, the physical condition of our school did not cause any serious problems." (P6).*

Technological Problems

Table 1.1. When examined, the problems of the participants arising from the technological equipment were collected in the categories of internet infrastructure and access problems, lack of tablets and computers in the classrooms that switched to distance education, and power outage. The majority of the participants stated that the poor internet infrastructure negatively affects the distance education process. *"Our students have limited access to the internet and technology as the*

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internet infrastructure is not sufficient in the school's environment. This situation creates a problem for the classes that have to take distance education." (P1).

Participants ; stated that the whole class switched to distance education after at least 2 students in a class in their school had a corona case. In this case, every student needs unlimited internet, phone, tablet or computer in order to participate effectively in the lessons conducted remotely. *"The fact that there is no computer or tablet at home and that students have to connect to the lesson by phone affects the process negatively." (P2). "The number of class participation was low in classes that switched to distance education due to the lack of internet and lack of tablets and computers." (P17).*

Participants stated that the power cuts in their regions put them in a difficult situation. *"We experienced a lot of power cuts, the need for a generator was felt" (K15).*

Eight of the participants stated that they did not experience any problems arising from the technological equipment due to the face-to-face education and the sufficient technological equipment in their schools. *"We did not have any problems because of the face-to-face training." (P4). "We did not experience any technological problems because we have smart boards and the internet." (P6).*

Top Management Issues

Table 1.1. When examined, the problems experienced by the participants with the senior management; material supply, last-minute articles, and irritating rhetoric in sudden information requests and teacher shortages. Participants in the pandemic process

They stated that they were insufficient in terms of materials and masks that the top management had to meet. They emphasized that this situation negatively affected the pandemic process. *"We had problems with the supply of masks and the lack of materials required by the senior management. The number of masks they*

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sent is never enough. The masks we have are about to run out and the situation negatively affects the process." (P11).

The participants stated that they experienced problems because the senior management suddenly asked for information late, even outside working hours, and did so in an uncomfortable manner."We had problems with the senior management due to urgent last-minute texts and disturbing attitudes about oratory in the late hours." (P15).

Participants stated that if the students in the classrooms who switched to distance education during the pandemic process turned negative after a 5-day quarantine, they could participate in face-to-face education at school. They stated that they felt the need. They stated that they had a problem in this regard."5 days after the whole class switched to distance education.

If the student's test turns negative, they can participate in face-to-face education. However, the classroom teacher provides distance education. Which teacher will provide face-to-face education? We had a teacher problem in this regard.

Twelve of the participants stated that they did not have a problem with the senior management.

FINDINGS RELATED TO THE METHODS OF COATING WITH THE PROBLEMS FACED BY SCHOOL MANAGERS

In this part of the research, the findings regarding the methods of solving the problems of school administrators are included. The answers given to the participants to the question "How did you try to solve the problems you experienced in terms of school administration in the first semester of the 2021-2022 academic year?" were collected in three categories. Table 4.2. When examined, the themes of school administrators about solution methods to problems counseling and assistance, legal practice and grouped as their own knowledge and experience.

Table 1.2. they encountered to the problems for Yes Type Solution Data on Those Who Developed the Methods

Category	Code	Quotation
Counseling and assistance	common sense, consultation School facilities, local facilities Parents' association, parent meetings	We consulted with our fellow teachers. We tried to manage the situation with a common mind. P5 We tried to solve the problems with local resources. P14 We use the school-parent union effectively, we attend parent meetings.
legal practice	Amount	When necessary, we kept a report for our unvaccinated teachers.K4

Own knowledge and experience	Banning entry to school	We banned the entrance to the school.K2
	HEPP code query	We asked for the HES code and vaccination card. We checked regularly every day. K3
	Effective communication, persuasion, negotiation	We tried to solve the problems we encountered by reconciliation. We used our human relations and effective persuasion power.
		Thanks to our effective communication skills
		We solved the problems. K16

Table 1.2. When examined, the participants stated that they solved the problems they encountered by consulting with other teacher friends, parents, the school family union and the people around the school that they could get help from."We tried to solve the problems in cooperation with our teachers. We consulted. We tried to manage the situation with a common mind." (P5). "We use the school-parent union effectively, we attend parent meetings, we express our wishes and expectations, and we listen to them." (P1).They also stated that they exchanged ideas and experiences by using the school facilities and with other administrators."We tried to solve the problems with local facilities. We asked for help from the people closest to the subject." '(K14).

The participants stated that they use effective communication and persuasion in solving the problems arising from the teachers, students, parents, physical environment, technology and senior management, and that they keep minutes by

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writing official letters when necessary. *"We went the way of persuading our unvaccinated teachers, we kept our minutes when necessary."* (P4).

Participants stated that they mostly solved the problems they encountered with their own knowledge and experience. Participants were affected by the uncontrolled disease during the pandemic period.

They stated that they prohibit entry to the school for parents who persistently want to enter the school garden and building in order to prevent the spread of the disease. *"Since it would be very difficult to get parents to the school with the HES code, we banned the entrance to the school."* (P2). Some of the participants stated that they put security at the school entrance in order to control the entrances to the school and they regularly inquire about the HEPP code every day. *"We put an attendant at the door. We asked for the HES code and vaccination card. We received the HES codes of our students and parents, and we checked them every day to ensure that those in quarantine stay at home."* (P3).

Participants stated that problems can be solved through effective communication, persuasion and compromise. *"We tried to solve the problems we encountered by reconciling with both parents and teachers."* (P8). *"We tried to solve the problems by using our human relations and effective persuasion power."* (P12). *"We solved the problems thanks to our effective communication method and our persuasion ability."* (P16).

FINDINGS RELATED TO SCHOOL MANAGERS' SOLUTIONS TO COPE WITH THE PROBLEMS THEY FACE

In this part of the study, the solution suggestions brought by the school administrators to the problems were emphasized. "What other alternatives could there be to solve the problems you experienced in terms of school management in the first semester of the 2021-2022 academic year? The answers to the question " were collected in 6 categories. When Table 1.3 is examined, the themes related to school administrators' suggestions for solutions to problems are caused by teachers, students, parents, physical facilities of the school, technology-based and senior management. grouped as solutions. Table 1.3. given in.

Table 1.3. Data on Suggestions for Solutions to the Problems They Encounter

Category	Code	Quotation
Suggestions for solutions to teacher-related problems	Seriousness and strict rules	The issue of pandemic should be approached more seriously.
	Persuasion	There should be strict rules and sanctions. K 10 We went to the way of persuasion about the vaccine. K4
	Effective communication	Communication should be given more priority. K12
Suggestions for solutions to student-related problems	hanging banners	Posters should be hung on the walls for the seriousness of the situation.K4
	Eating in class	We closed the cafeteria due to the excess of students and the small size of the cafeteria.P2
	Mask distribution	School for unmasked students

Disinfectant
application

Mask should be given at the
entrance.K2

Disinfectant should be placed
in school corridors,
classrooms, and toilets.

Table 1.3. Continued Data on Suggestions for Solutions to the Problems They Encounter

Category	Code	Quotation
Suggestions for solutions to parent-related problems	parent education	It is necessary to raise awareness by conducting regular parent trainings. K17
	information meetings	Information meetings should be held. K6
	Security	Every school should be given a security guard. K3
physical of the school Suggestions for solutions to problems arising from the possibilities	Class size reduction	Class sizes should be fixed at maximum 20.K3
	renovation	Renovation works should be done during the summer holidays.K9

Suggestions for Solutions to the Problems Originated by the Teacher

In their suggestions for solutions to the problems arising from the teacher, the participants stated that more effective communication and persuasion should be used, and they also did this in this way. *"We tried to convince our teachers about vaccination." (P4). "Healthy communication is the basis of healthy governance. More emphasis should be placed on communication." (K12).* Again, due to the fact that the pandemic process is a very sensitive process, the participants

They stated that strict rules should be set and the situation should be taken more seriously in order to prevent possible problems that will negatively affect the process. *"The issue of pandemic should be approached more seriously." (P8).*

The participants stated that they thought that teachers should know their responsibilities well while doing their jobs, they should be more careful because they are role models for students and parents, and they should be more sensitive about vaccines and PCR tests.

Suggestions for Solutions to Student-Related Problems

For the solution of the problems caused by the students during the pandemic process; They stated that it is very important to inform and that they hang posters at the school for this purpose. They stated that posters should be given importance because they attract the attention of children. *"Posters should be hung on the walls in order to understand the seriousness of the situation." (P4).*

The participants stated that they went down to the dining hall to eat during lunch breaks, but due to the small size of the cafeteria and the unmasked environment, they closed the cafeterias and let them eat in the classrooms. They stated that this practice should continue. *"Due to the large number of students eating at school during the lunch break and the small size of the cafeteria, we closed the*

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cafeteria in terms of social distance. This should be done in schools with small cafeterias." (P2).

Participants stated the importance of mask and disinfectant application. They stated that masks should be given to students who come to school without masks, that disinfectants placed in the corridors and classrooms of the school should be checked and filled regularly, and that children should be warned to use them. *"Unmasked students should be given masks at the school garden entrance in the mornings." (P2). "Disinfectants should be placed in school corridors, classrooms and toilets, and students should be warned about using them frequently." (P1).*

Suggestions for Solutions to Problems Caused by Parents

For the solution of the problems caused by the participants and the parents; stated the necessity of holding parent information meetings and regular parent trainings. *"Awareness should be increased by conducting regular parent trainings" (K17). "Extra information meetings should be held for parents" (P6).* Again, the participants stated that the pandemic process should be taken more seriously and they did their best to prevent it from disrupting education, and stated that the parents did not take the situation as seriously as they did, they did not carry the HEPP code and they did not want to have the HEPP code questioned. In order not to confront the parents, it is necessary to have a security guard in every school and that the HES code query can be done in this way.

Stated that they should do it. *"Every school should be given a security guard and the HEPP code should be questioned." (P3).*

Suggestions for Solutions to the Problems Originated from the Physical Facilities of the School

Participants stated that in order to solve the problems arising from the physical environment, the class size should not be more than 20 people, so that the social distance rule can only be applied effectively. *"Class sizes should be fixed at 20 at most." (K3).* Again, the participants stated that the renovation works should not

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be done during the pandemic process, and that the renovations should be done during the summer holidays when there are no students at the school. *"Renovation works should be done during the summer holidays in a way that will not adversely affect the process."* (K9).

Suggestions for Solutions to the Problems Caused by the Education System

Participants address the problems arising from the education system; They stated that there should be diluted education and that there should be a dual system in schools. *"Diluted education should be started."* (P4). *"Schools in the whole country should switch to a dual system"* (P2).

The participants stated that a sub-unit related to the needs of the schools should be established in the municipalities, so that it is possible to meet the needs more easily and quickly.. *"A sub-unit should be established in municipalities only to meet the needs of schools."* (K15).

Participants stated that students who have been studying distance education for a long time experience academic regression and that compensation programs are very important to close this gap. *"More importance should be given to make-up programs"* (K19). They stated that the pandemic process of the participants caused a change in all educational activities and stated that in-service training should be given importance in order to manage this change in the best way. *"More importance should be given to in-service training"* (P11).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this section, the problems faced by the school administrators participating in the research during the Covid-19 pandemic process and solution suggestions are emphasized. The results obtained as a result of the interviews with the school administrators were discussed and included in the suggestion section. 19 school administrators working in primary, secondary and high schools in Kocaeli province Dilovası district were included in the research.

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The first sub-problem of the research is the problem of what problems school administrators face during the Covid-19 pandemic process. In this context, it was concluded that the problems that school administrators faced during the Covid-19 pandemic period were caused by teachers, students, parents, physical facilities of the school, technology and senior management. Based on the results obtained, it was concluded that school administrators faced many problems during the Covid-19 pandemic period and that the problems they encountered had many different sources. Based on this, it has been concluded that school administrators face many problems at the same time and that the problems may be caused by human factors as well as non-human factors such as technological infrastructure or physical facilities. In the study conducted in Özdögrü (2021), the problems faced by school principals in school management during the Covid-19 outbreak were examined. Similar to this study, school principals faced many problems in the Covid-19 outbreak. These problems are management, communication, financing, planning, personnel, school climate and school health and the problems encountered in the education and training process.

It has been concluded that the problems stemming from the teacher are giving PCR tests, anti-vaccination and resistance to the vaccine, and lack of teachers. Based on the results obtained, it can be commented that teachers are hesitant about getting vaccinated, which is a new situation, and they are not willing to vaccinate, and this situation poses a problem for school administrators. The fact that non-vaccinated teachers were asked to give PCR tests and that teachers were not willing to give PCR tests very often also caused school administrators to have problems with teachers. Having teachers who are worried about their own health during the pandemic period and having a chronic illness

The fact that teachers are on administrative leave has led to a shortage of teachers in schools and this has created a problem for school administrators. There are also school administrators who stated that they did not experience any problems caused by teachers. In the study conducted by Külekçi Akyavuz and Çakın (2020), it was found that there were problems caused by teachers. The indifference of teachers

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during the pandemic period has caused problems. Likewise, in the study conducted by Sarı and Nayır (2020), Covid-19 caused teachers to experience stress, and this situation caused teachers to feel bad and caused problems.

It has been concluded that the problems caused by the student are due to non-compliance with social distance, absenteeism, not wanting to wear a mask, being a carrier of disease, academic regression, adaptation problem, school commitment, hygiene and cleanliness. The fact that the students are active, want to communicate with each other, and the school buildings, classrooms and the school garden are not large caused the students not to pay attention to the social distance, and this caused the school administrators to have problems in controlling the social distance. The inability of the student who was caught or in contact with the Covid-19 disease to attend school has caused the students to have problems of absenteeism, and the school administrators have caused problems in ensuring the regular attendance of the students to the school. School administrators had to constantly warn about wearing masks and had problems with the use of masks due to the fact that the students were younger and could not understand the seriousness of the Covid-19 pandemic process. Since the symptoms of Covid-19 disease in children cannot be seen well enough, it has been concluded that the possibility of students being carriers of the disease is another problem faced by school administrators. Parents of students are willing to send students to school because they are afraid of falling behind academically, and this situation accelerates the transmission of the disease. The inability of students to attend school due to illness causes a decline in students' academic achievement. In two cases, it caused school administrators to face problems. Schools continue in distance education for a long time during the covid-19 pandemic process.

The transition to face-to-face education after the school's education caused the school administrators to encounter problems in terms of ensuring the adaptation of students to the school and trying to ensure their commitment to the school. Due to the young age of the students, the students did not comply with the cleaning and hygiene rules that they should pay attention to during the Covid-19 pandemic period,

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and this caused the school administrators to not perform the cleaning and hygiene rules as desired. Similar to the study conducted by Külekçi Akyavuz and Çakın (2020), school administrators stated that they had problems caused by students during the Covid-19 pandemic period. Due to the communication problems with the students and the lack of face-to-face communication, various problems have arisen from the students.

It has been concluded that the problems caused by the parents are due to not wearing masks, not complying with social distance, wanting to enter the school garden and the building, not carrying the HES code, not complying with the entrance time to the school, and sending sick children to school. The fact that parents are not sufficiently conscious about wearing masks has caused school administrators to frequently warn and have problems with the use of masks. The high number of students, the young age of the students and the fact that the parents brought the students to the school themselves caused the parents not to pay attention to the social distance, and in this case, the school administrators had problems. The fact that the parents of the students wanted to enter the school garden and inside the school building due to the lack of awareness caused the school administrators to constantly confront the parents, and this situation created a problem for the school administrators. The fact that the parents of the students do not know the HEPP codes or do not have a device that can show the HEPP code with them has caused the school administrators to have problems constantly because it is not possible for the parents to enter the school without questioning the HEPP code. The fact that the parents of the students sent or brought the students to the school before the determined school hours caused problems in terms of ensuring social distance and this situation created a problem for the school administrators. As a result of the fact that the parents are not conscious enough to have the students take the Covid-19 test, they also send their children who have the disease to school.

This situation caused the spread of the disease within the school to increase and this situation created a problem for school administrators. There are also school administrators who state that they do not have any problems caused by parents.

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Similar to the results obtained from the study, it is seen that school administrators have problems originating from parents in the study conducted in Öz Dođru (2021). Inability of parents to use communication tools well enough and having difficulties in communicating caused school administrators to experience problems arising from parents.

It has been concluded that the problems arising from physical facilities are due to the large number of classrooms, the insufficient width of the garden, corridor and stairs, the lack of sinks due to renovations, the guest school, the dual system, and the insufficient building. The large number of classrooms and the inability of the students to act adequately and in the desired manner in terms of social distance caused the school administrators to have problems. Likewise, the inadequacy of the school garden, corridor and the width of the stairs caused students to have problems in ensuring that they pay attention to social distance. The decrease in the number of sinks that students can use due to the renovations in the schools has caused school administrators to have problems in terms of ensuring hygiene and cleanliness during the Covid-19 pandemic process. As a result of the renovation works carried out in the schools, the transfer of students to other schools and the implementation of the dual education system caused the number of existing students to double. Due to this situation, the lack of time required to pay attention to social distance and to ensure the cleanliness and hygiene of schools caused school administrators to encounter problems. There are also school administrators who state that they do not have any problems due to physical facilities. Similar to the results obtained from the study, it is seen that school administrators have problems in terms of physical facilities. School administrators stated that they had difficulties in the study, especially in terms of providing social distance. In this case, it caused school administrators to experience problems arising from physical facilities.

It was concluded that the problems arising from the technological hardware were caused by the internet infrastructure and access problems, the lack of tablet computers in the classrooms that switched to distance education, and the power outage. Since the environment where the schools are located is a region where there

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are problems in terms of internet infrastructure and access, it has caused the classes that have switched to distance education to not be able to attend the classes sufficiently, and it has caused the school administrators to encounter problems in ensuring the attendance of the students to the lessons. As a result of the economic inadequacies arising from the environment in which the schools are located, the problem of lack of tablets and computers for the classes that continue distance education has come to light, and this has caused the school administrators to have problems in ensuring the attendance of the students to the lessons. Continuous power cuts due to the infrastructure of the environment where the schools are located have caused disruptions in the use of technological tools. It has caused schools to experience the need for generators and this has created a problem for school administrators. There are also school administrators who state that they have never experienced any problems caused by technological equipment. In the study conducted in Grasshopper and Cut (2021), it was concluded that, similar to this study, the education process was negatively affected due to the fact that the students were not in good economic condition during the pandemic period, and they did not have technological equipment such as computers, internet and television.

It has been concluded that the problems stemming from the senior management are due to masks, inadequacy in the supply of materials, last-minute letters, sudden information requests, uncomfortable oratory, and teacher shortage in classrooms that have switched to distance education. Considering the number of students in the schools, this situation caused the school administrators to have problems in the supply of masks and materials, since a sufficient number of masks were not sent for the students and sufficient cleaning materials were not delivered to the schools to ensure the cleanliness and hygiene of the school. It was a problem for school administrators to request articles from the school administration in a short time and usually to get last minute information and to express them inappropriately in terms of style. It is seen that the time period for resuming face-to-face education differs for students and teachers in the conditions determined at the point of returning to the school again.

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This has caused school administrators to have problems in finding teachers to take their classes when students come to school. There are also school administrators who state that they do not have any problems arising from the senior management. Similar to this study, in the study conducted by Özdogru (2021), it was found that many problems arise due to the constant changes in the decisions, the unclear and comprehensible decisions, the use of other channels instead of the official channels, the managers need to take too much initiative, and the weak cooperation with the stakeholders. conclusion has been reached.

The second sub-problem of the research is the problem of what are the methods of coping with the problems faced by school administrators during the Covid-19 pandemic process. In this context, it has been concluded that school administrators attach importance to solidarity and cooperation in coping with the problems they encountered during the Covid-19 pandemic, benefit from legal practices and use their own knowledge and experience. When the results obtained are examined, it has been concluded that school administrators try to use different methods that vary from problem to problem and are suitable for solving the problem in order to solve the problems they encounter. Similar to this study, in the study conducted by Öz Doğru (2021), school administrators expressed the methods they use to cope with the problems they encounter. In the study, the opinions of school principals were examined in two parts as administrative and individual strategies.

It was concluded that school administrators preferred common sense, consultation, benefiting from school and local opportunities, organizing school parent union and parent meetings at the point of solving problems by using counseling and cooperation method. It is concluded that the problems experienced at the point of common mind and consultation are shared with the teachers and different thoughts and different perspectives are reached at the point of problem solving by including the teachers in the problem solving process, and this situation enables the problems to be solved more easily and in a shorter time. Since the problem must be solved quickly at the point of solving the problems encountered, the school has its own

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It has been tried to use the facilities or the local facilities around the school, and it has been concluded that this situation contributes to solving the problems more quickly at the point of coping with the problems. Since the problems encountered are shared with the parents, parents are informed about the problems by holding school parent-teacher associations and parent meetings. In the study conducted by Öz Dođru (2021), similar to this study, it was concluded that school administrators use methods such as getting support from other school administrators and consultation at the point of coping with problems.

It has been concluded that the problems are tried to be solved by using the method of keeping minutes at the point of solving the problems by using the legal practice method. It has been tried to give official validity to the problem by keeping a record of the problems encountered when and where necessary during the Covid-19 process, and it has been concluded that it will contribute to the solution of the problems by emphasizing the importance of the problem.

It has been concluded that the problems are tried to be solved by using their own knowledge and experience to solve the problems, by using the methods of banning the entrance to the school, asking the HES code, and effective communication and reconciliation methods. It has been concluded that the way of prohibiting parents from entering the school is preferred because it is not possible for parents to be admitted to the school without questioning the HES code, and this situation causes school administrators to encounter problems in doing their current job. It has been ensured that students and parents are not allowed to enter the school before the end of the quarantine period, by requesting the HEPP code information of the students and checking them regularly every day. It was concluded that measures were taken by looking at the HES codes and vaccination card information of the parents who wanted to enter the school. It has been concluded that school administrators prefer to intervene in problems by communicating well with their interlocutors in the face of the problems they encounter and by resorting to various reconciliation methods on the issues they disagree with. Gripper and Cut

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(2021), it was concluded that, similar to the results obtained from this study, they used methods such as acting calmly against problems, using their empathy skills, and being motivating by using their own knowledge and experience.

The third sub-problem of the research is the problem of what solutions are offered for the methods of coping with the problems faced by school administrators during the Covid-19 pandemic process. School administrators offered alternative solutions to the problems they encountered during the Covid-19 pandemic process, such as offering solutions to the problems arising from the teacher, students, parents, the physical facilities of the school, and the education system, according to the sources of the problems encountered.

It has been concluded that the solution proposals brought against the problems arising from the teacher are in the form of seriousness and strict rules, persuasion and effective communication. School administrators stated that ensuring that teachers approach the pandemic process seriously and that more precise and strict rules are taken, especially about vaccination, will be beneficial in terms of managing the course of the pandemic in schools more accurately. It has been concluded that providing effective communication against those who do not want to be vaccinated, emphasizing the importance of the vaccine, explaining why it is necessary and ensuring that they are persuaded will contribute to the solution of the problems of not vaccinating the teachers. Similar to this study, in the study conducted by Döş and Cömert (2012), school administrators drew attention to the importance of providing effective communication in crisis situations in solving problems.

It was concluded that the solution suggestions brought against the problems caused by the students were hanging posters, eating in the classroom, distribution of masks, and disinfectant application. It has been concluded that the Covid-19 process can be noticed by the students by ensuring that the students realize the importance of the situation, get information about the process, and hang up posters in various parts of the school about what they should pay attention to. Since the number of students eating lunch at schools is high and school cafeterias

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It has been concluded that the school cafeteria can be closed and the practice of eating in classrooms can be started because it is small at the point of maintaining social distance. Students can come to school without wearing masks because they do not have enough awareness about the use of masks. It has been concluded that masks can be distributed to students who do not have a mask while entering the school in order to prevent them from entering the school without wearing a mask. It has been concluded that disinfectant can be placed in school corridors, classrooms and toilets in order to give importance to cleanliness and hygiene at the point of disease prevention and to ensure that students pay more attention to cleanliness and hygiene. In the study carried out by Özdogru (2021), it was concluded that the sources of the problem were first identified and the identified problems were resolved.

It has been concluded that the solution proposals brought against the problems caused by the parents are in the form of parent education, information meetings and security. Since it is seen and known that the parents do not show a fully conscious attitude towards the disease, it has been concluded that it may be beneficial to hold parent trainings and information meetings in order to show the necessary diligence and seriousness of the parents. It has been concluded that it may be beneficial to assign security guards to schools in order to alleviate the workload of the school administration in this regard, since the HEPP code inquiries should be made at the entrance of the school.

It has been concluded that the solution proposals brought against the problems arising from the physical facilities of the school are in the form of reducing the class size and renovating. It has been concluded that it may be beneficial to reduce the class size in schools where the number of students in the classes is high, as social distance should be observed in order to prevent the transmission of the disease. Since the renovations in the schools cause the students in the schools to move to other schools, the increase in the number of students in the school that has been moved creates a problem for the school administration in terms of providing cleanliness, hygiene and social distance. In order to prevent this situation, it was

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concluded that it would be beneficial to carry out the renovation works related to the school during the summer holidays.

It has been concluded that the solution proposals brought against the problems arising from the physical facilities of the school are diluted education, dual system, compensation program, sub-unit in the municipality, in-service training. It has been concluded that it may be beneficial to switch to a diluted education system or dual education system, since the high number of students causes problems in ensuring cleanliness, hygiene and social distance, and it is seen that they cannot be fully provided. It has been concluded that the implementation of compensatory programs may be beneficial in reducing learning losses, as it causes learning losses in students due to the implementation of distance education over a long period of time during the Covid-19 pandemic process. It has been concluded that it would be beneficial to create sub-units in municipalities and meet the needs of schools by these units, since schools need economic support, especially in terms of ensuring cleanliness and hygiene. It has been concluded that in-service training may be beneficial in order to enable teachers to adapt to the changes experienced during the Covid-19 pandemic process and to better continue their distance education activities, which have largely entered our education system during the Covid-19 pandemic period. In the study conducted by Özdögrü (2021), it was stated that the problems encountered can be solved by exhibiting exemplary behaviors of school administrators in terms of technological leadership, effectively monitoring and evaluating the deficiencies.

UGGESTIONS

Recommendations for Practitioners

- During the Covid-19 pandemic, teachers may not be willing to give PCR tests and not be vaccinated. By using necessary information activities and a good communication method, teachers can be provided with PCR tests and vaccinations by acting in line with legal practices.

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· During the Covid-19 pandemic, students are encouraged to hang posters in the designated places of the school, switch to the practice of eating in the classrooms instead of the cafeteria, and distribute the masks to students when entering the school, since they do not pay enough attention to social distance, use of masks, cleaning and hygiene.

It can be ensured that the application of disinfectant in classrooms, corridors and toilets.

- Since it is difficult to maintain social distance in the classrooms during the Covid-19 pandemic process, it may be possible to reduce the number of classrooms and to carry out the renovation works related to the school in the summer months when the students are not at school.
- Since it is important to raise the awareness of the parents of the students during the Covid-19 pandemic process, parent information training can be provided. Parent entrances to the school may be prohibited, except for mandatory conditions. It can be ensured that the HES codes of students and parents are checked on a regular basis every day. In order to ensure that HEPP code inquiries are made, a security guard can be assigned to each school.
- In order to reduce the spread of the disease during the Covid-19 pandemic process, a transition to diluted education or dual education system can be provided. Compensatory education can be applied in order to eliminate the existing learning deficiencies in students. School needs can be met by establishing sub-units in municipalities. Teachers' awareness can be raised by increasing the number of in-service training activities for teachers.

Suggestions to Researchers

- The research was carried out with the participation of school administrators working in primary, secondary and high schools in Kocaeli province Dilovası district. By including more than one district in the same province in the research, it can be checked whether the results obtained differ.

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- The research was carried out with the participation of school principals working in primary, secondary and high schools in Kocaeli province Dilovası district. By including vice principals and chief vice principals in the research, it can be checked whether the problems encountered differ.
- In the study, semi-structured interview forms with school administrators were used to collect data. Observation method can be used to ensure data diversity.
- The research was carried out with the participation of school administrators working in primary, secondary and high schools in Kocaeli province Dilovası district. Parents, teachers and students can be included in the research process to see if the problems encountered differ in terms of the parties.
- The research was conducted with the participation of 19 school administrators from primary, secondary and high schools in Kocaeli province Dilovası district. It can be ensured that more school administrators participate in the research.

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